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Terms and terminology

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Abstract: In the article, we discussed the relationship between the disciplines of terms and terminology and the work done so far.

Key words: term, terminology, word formation, scientific terms, word.

Introduction: Terms can appear, usually on the basis of the internal capabilities of a particular language, or from an external source, that is, assimilation, translation from other languages. Since the middle of the 20th century, the Uzbek language has entered the Uzbek language, along with many international words, as well as terms related to the fields of science, technology, sports, and culture. As a result, learning natural sciences, sports and technology in Uzbek became difficult. With the granting of the right to the Uzbek language as the state language and the achievement of independence of Uzbekistan, the negative trend in this regard began to end. Because the Uzbek language does not lag behind any other language in the world either lexically, grammatically, or stylistically. On the contrary, our mother tongue, our great thinker, Hazrat Alisher Navoi, proved in his work "Muhokamatul Lug'atayn" that it has more possibilities than some languages in terms of creating words and expressing subtleties of meaning.

Research results and methods: The terms can initially be divided into two large groups. 1. Vocational terms. 2. Scientific terms. Vocational terms have long been used to express the concepts of animal husbandry, farming, pottery, blacksmithing, carpentry, carpet making, embroidery, cooking, confectionary, medicine and many other such professions, which have been developed as a profession by our people. Scientific terms also have a plural history. Because they are related to the creation of the works of our great-grandfathers, M. Koshghari, Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Al-Khorazmi, Az-Zamakhshari, A. Navai, Babur, and other encyclopedic scholars. appeared directly. In general, scientific terms are widely used today in hundreds of modern sciences such as linguistics, literary studies, music, history, pedagogy,

psychology, biology, medicine, geography, astronomy, physics, mathematics, law, chemistry, geology, mineralogy, philosophy, economics. is being used. Our students, who are graduating from a higher educational institution in a certain specialty, are required to master the terms related to social-political, spiritual-educational fields and their specialty, and have a sufficient idea about them.

Terminology is one of the current directions of modern linguistic research. Currently, the growth of the issue of terminology is considered, on the one hand, due to the increase of new concepts due to the dynamic development of science, on the other hand, it is explained as a phenomenon related to the insufficient study of issues such as the process of formation, development and function of terms. .

Discussion of results: Terminology is a very large part of the vocabulary of every language. It is not for nothing that it develops very quickly, because it allows you to make new words. The terminology of a language consists of a system of many terms. A word or combination of words in a particular field of knowledge, industry or culture is called a term. The meaning of a word expressed by the term is interpreted by explaining it in a thematic literature. As new technologies penetrate more and more fields, the terminology of that field is constantly expanding. One such field is the field of polygraphy and publishing, which is engaged in book publishing today. If we pay attention to the development of this field, the entry of technical means into this field mainly coincides with the beginning of the twentieth century. But its most advanced period is today. Today's modern polygraphy-publishing network has become one of the leading industries in which technical tools are used, incorporating the processes of preparation of documents and reproduction of their copies, turning them into books. As a result, many new concepts and new scientific and technical terms are entering the terminology of this field. In all the works devoted to terminology, the units that represent specific concepts of one or another field, have a definition, and mainly perform a nominative function are considered to be terms. A.Reformatsky defines the term and concludes that "...terms are special words". AVKalinin calls the words used in certain disciplines and professions "special lexicon" and divides it into two groups. 1. The special lexicon includes, first of all, terms. 2. In addition to terms, the special lexicon also includes professionalisms. It is known that the level of development and improvement of each field of science is inextricably linked with such signs as the level of development and regulation of the terminology of this field. Because if the term used

in scientific literature or its form of expression is not clear and unambiguous, negative situations such as confusion and ambiguity will certainly remain. Therefore, as VPDanilenko noted, the progress indicator of each science or field is also determined by the fact that the terminology of this field has "strict scientific terminology". VPDanilenko here refers to the concept of "rigorous scientific terminology" as the compatibility of any field terminology with the development of this field of science, the coherence of field terminology in the expression of concepts related to the same field, the compatibility of the created and circulating terminology with a specific scientific language. Terminology represents a certain defined system of understanding reality and is one of the channels of intellectual communication. According to Vinogradov, "There are two sides, two points of view of creating and defining terms: language structure and understanding, semantic conditionally the development of one or another system of understanding in science" (V. Vinogradov, "Voprosy yazykoznaniya" 1961, str. 3-10). The change of terms in linguistics and the emergence of new terms are inextricably linked with the development of science and technology. About this, the linguist scientist LIBojno states the following: "Under the influence of technical development, terminology changes based on two interrelated laws, firstly, with the laws of scientific and technical progress, and secondly, in connection with the general laws of language development."

DSLotte spoke about what categories of words can be terminable: "in technology, the main categories meaning the following concepts are terminable: processes (events); technical items (materials, weapons, tools, details, etc.); properties; calculation concepts (parameters, geometric figures, etc.); units of measurement" (Lotte D.S. Osnovy postroeniya nauchnotekhnicheskoy terminologii. Voprosy teorii i metodiki. M., 1961. - p. 29.), and AVKalinin tries to justify the fact that the words term and profession are different from each other as follows: "a term is an official, accepted and legalized concept of a certain science, industrial field, agriculture, technology is an expression, a name, and the words of profession are a semi-official word that is often spread among a profession, specialty, and does not have a strict, scientific description of the concept" (Kalinin A. V. Leksika russkogo yazyka:, 1971. – p. 141.). Prof. about Uzbek terminology. U. Tursunov's thoughts are also important for our linguistics today. KMMusayev compares terminology as the lexicon of the language to a city. According to him, although the terminology is built on the basis of a single plan, it is not built at

once. It is formed on the basis of historical conditions, various architects, designers, inventors of different generations participate in its creation. They build every structure that is being built with good research. The specific complexity in the regulation of terminology is determined by this (Musaev K. M. Formirovanie, razvitie i sovremennye problemy terminologii. 1986. -p.163). At the same time, it is possible to point out the works of NABaskov, NKDmitriyev, FSFaseyev, and later BUOruzbayeva, RAUrekenova, M.Sh. Gasimov on the study of terms based on the materials of Turkic languages. Professor Renat Doniyorov is one of the scientists who made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek language terminology. In his book "Some issues of the technical terminology of the Uzbek language" (1977), issues such as regulating the technical terminology of the Uzbek language and preventing a number of confusions in it are included. This work can be said to be a great contribution to the research of technical terminology. On the basis of materials of Russian, English, German, French languages, terms related to such fields as socio-political, economic, sociological, legal, agricultural, pharmaceutical, profession, linguistics, literary studies were studied. In this field, serious research has been carried out in Uzbekistan [O. Usmanov, U. Tursunov, S. Ibrohimov, R. Doniyorov, H. Dadaboyev, N. Mahmudov, A. Madvaliyev, Y. Ibrohimov, N. Mahkamov, A. Sobirov, H. Jabborov and others]. Current at the time of terminology the following types according to _ scientific research take is going

1. **Theoretical terminology** develops the rules of use and development of terms.
2. **Practical (prikladnoye)** terminology deals with description, regulation, standardization, and translation of terms.
3. **General terminology** studies the general characteristics of terms, problems related to their occurrence, composition, and use.
4. **Special or field terminology** analyzes the terms of a language taken separately. This type of terminology is more developed in Uzbekistan.
5. **Typological terminology** compares terms within one or several languages. The scope of such studies is very narrow.
6. **Semasiological terminology** studies the relation of terms with semantics, meaning change, polysemy, homonymy, synonymy, etc.
7. **Onomasiological terminology** deals with the creation of terms, their composition, and the selection of their alternatives.

8. **Historical terminology** studies the linguistic and non-linguistic factors of the origin of terms. Experts in the field associate the emergence of anthro-linguistics with historical terminology .

9. **Functional terminology** studies the use of terms in speech, their place in the computer system.

10. **Cognitive** (or epistemological) terminology deals with determining the place of terms in human thinking.

The above shows that terminology has already been formed as a special science. At the same time, it is not without problems that await its clear and objective solution. These, in our opinion, are:

- to thoroughly analyze the opinions expressed about whether the term is a word, phrase or function and come to the appropriate conclusion;

- as long as the term appears in the form of a word combination, it is necessary to deeply study the term of the word combination itself, to prove that V.V. Vinogradov's thoughts are a one-sided and logically empty definition, to get out of its influence, to find new and reacting to reasonable opinions (Khojayev, Beloshapkova, V.Y. Plotkin);

- to continue the research related to the definition of mutual similarities and differences of terms and nomen, terminology and nomenclature;

- a broad and detailed description of concepts such as preterm, terminoid, prototerm, which are directly related to the understanding of the essence of the term:

- recognizing that the term and the sectoral (special, private) lexicon are synonymous terms that express exactly the same concept, and based on the principle that the presence of synonyms in the use of terms is unpleasant, achieving the consistent use of the first of them (in our opinion, the term) ;

- to continue the work of creating bilingual and multilingual terminological dictionaries:

- conducting comparative terminological studies on a large scale:

- creation of national terminology. Adhering to the laws and regulations of the Uzbek language when learning foreign terms;

- taking into account the importance of terminology in science and education, including the subject "Terminology Basics" in the curriculum of all faculties and departments of higher educational institutions:

- to search for forgotten terms, to bring them into circulation selectively, for this purpose it is advisable to consistently continue studying the language and terminology of classic scientific works. In this, the tolerance characteristic of our people should be accepted as a priority principle;

- and finally: terminology is an important component of the nomination. The theory of nomination was deeply developed by Prof. VGGak. Therefore, any researcher who wants to deal with issues of terminology should not only know this theory, but also be able to creatively use its principles [see: Gak, 1977,1980].

Conclusion: Terms and terminology, such changes have expanded the scope of the Uzbek language and enriched its lexical structure with new scientific and technical terms.

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